

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

NXPH1 (neurexophilin 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	30010 / P58417
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
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Therapeutic Area(s)	Alzheimer's disease
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Bioinformatic analysis: Target source & hypothesis

Protein constructs & expression methods: NXPH1_22-271_AviN_HisC.Baculovirus expression for structure determination

TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.93 (rank #494, 98th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target's general relevance to Alzheimer's Disease, and is the sum of the target's Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 2.77 out of 5 (rank #6421, 74.3th percentile). The individual score components include 1.24 of 3 for genetics, and 1.53 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of NXPH1 RNA is significantly decreased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. NXPH1 is annotated to GO terms from the Synapse domain.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
2.773	6421	74.28	1.244	1.529

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Seattle Alzheimer's Disease Brain Cell Atlas (SEA-AD). The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins. The expression of the target in subtypes within each broad class is shown as a point. Blue points show the summary expression of cells from individuals with no dementia, while red points show summary metrics of cells from dementia patients. Open circles reflect low confidence measures of expression. The

expression of NXPH1 is confidently detected in both oligodendrocyte precursor cells (OPC) and inhibitory neuron sub-types within this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

NXPH1 is involved with developmental and homeostatic synaptic remodelling, particularly associated with modulation of GABA receptor content and subsequent synaptic plasticity(1-4). See the description below for a more detailed discussion of NXPH1 biology. The NXPH1 association with AD largely stems from its

role in shaping synaptic valence, and consistently, we identified it as a component of a core upregulated proteomic module that is tightly linked with AD pathology and clinical dementia (5). The project described here is the development of a target enablement package (TEP) for NXP1 to help future scientific investigations into NXP1's role in AD. The basic TEP includes validated antibodies that can be employed in both immunohistochemistry and biochemical studies, purified protein, and a full bioinformatic workup of NXP1's relationship to AD and AD biological domains. We hope that these resources will facilitate future investigations into the mechanism and association of NXP1 and AD.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

NXP1 (neurexophilin 1) is a 271 amino acid secreted protein involved in synaptic development (6, 7). Members of the neurexin and neuroligin families are genes that promote the stabilization and maturation of synapses after the initial axon pathfinding process results in the preliminary connections (8, 9). The role of neurexophilins is to modulate the interaction between the neurexin and neuroligins, which is suggested to be part of a structured wiring logic that impacts the emergent synaptic properties, such as the composition of receptors and channels (2). Given the high rate of synaptic remodelling, NXP1 may play a role in homeostatic synaptic maintenance and facilitation that occurs with learning and memory events(2). Consistently, members of the neurexin family associate with GABA receptors(4) and play a role in glutamate channels targeting to specific synapses (10, 11), and specifically regulate the presence of GABA receptors in the presynaptic connection (1), likely conferring both autocrine and paracrine gating mechanisms for synaptic vesicle release (3).

The NXP1 knockout mouse demonstrated attenuated short-term depression mediated by GABA receptor signalling in the cortex (3). Conversely, the over-expression of NXP1 decreases short-term potentiation at excitatory connections, which correlate with the histological observation of elevated GABA receptors proximal to the ectopically expressed NXP1 (3). These data support the model that the neurexin, neuroligin and neurexophilin families interact to modulate synaptic receptor content, and consequently impact the excitatory or inhibitory nature of the synapse (3, 8, 10). Our work within TREAT-AD identified NXP1 as part of a core proteomic module, module 42, dramatically elevated in AD that is highly statistically correlated with both neuropathological progression and clinical cognitive dementia (5). Given the long-standing observation that loss of GABA receptors and inhibitory synapses occur early in AD (12) and are modulated in several murine AD models (13, 14) supports the idea that NXP1 may play a role in early emergent AD pathology, the loss of NXP1 may give rise to excitotoxicity, and the elevation of NXP1 may represent an inborn physiological attempt at synaptic homeostasis. While speculative, the potential role of NXP1 playing a synaptic regulatory function that may be dysregulated in AD warrants further investigation by the scientific community.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Proteins Purified

1. NXP1_22-271_AviN_HisC. Baculovirus expression for structure determination.

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

Proteins Expression and Purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

Gene name	NXPH1
Uniprot ID	P58417
Region	22-271

Description	May be signaling molecules that resemble neuropeptides and that act by binding to alpha-neurexins and possibly other receptors.
Synonyms	Neurexophilin-1
Construct ID	NXPH1_22-271_AviN_HisC (PBC039-E01)
Parental Vector	pFHMSP-AviN-LIC-C
Tag (N-terminal)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAGSAGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSG
Tag (C-terminal)	EFVEHHHHHHHH
Protein mass (with tag)	35346.82 Da
Extinction Coefficient with tag ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	55725
Protein sequence (with tag)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAGSAGLNDIFEAQKIEWHEGSAGGSGANLTNGGKS ELLKSGSSKSTLKHIIWTESSKDLSISRLLSQTFRGKENDTDLRLRYDTPEPYSEQDLWD WLRNSTDLQEP RPRAKRRPIVKTGKFKMFGWGFHFSNIKTVKLNLLITGKIVDHG NGTFSVYFRHNSTGQGNVSVSLVPPTKIVEFDLAQQTVIDAKDSKSFNCRIEYKVDK ATKNTLCNYDPSKTCYQEQTQSHVSWLCSKPFKVICIYISFYSTDYKLVQKVC PDYNYH SDTPYFPSGEFVEHHHHHHHH

Purified Protein

<p>SEC (step 2):</p> <p>NXP1_22-271_AviN_Hi sC</p>	
<p>IEC (step 3):</p> <p>NXP1_22-271_AviN_Hi sC</p>	
<p>Intact Mass Deconvolution:</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Observed Mass:</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Protein yield:</p>	<p>1.2 mg/L of culture</p>

<p>Expression and Purification Protocol</p>	
<p>Expression host</p>	<p>Insect cells: Sf9 (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)</p>
<p>Expression Medium</p>	<p>I-Max Insect Media W/ L-Glutamine, Wisent Biocentre</p>
<p>Transformation and storage</p>	<p>The baculovirus expression vector system (BEVS), specifically Bac-to-Bac Expression System (Invitrogen), employing <i>Autographa californica</i> multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) has been used for expression screening and production of target protein. The plasmid transfer vector containing the gene of interest was transformed into DH10Bac <i>E. coli</i> competent cells to generate recombinant viral bacmid DNA. Adherent Sf9 cells were then transfected with bacmid DNA to generate recombinant viruses used for the baculovirus-mediated production in the insect cells.</p>

Expression	For the scale-up productions, suspension cultures of the baculovirus-infected insect cells, (SCBIC) were prepared by infection of the Sf9 cells with the corresponding P2 viruses. On the day of production, 2 L of Sf9 cells (cell viability > 97%) in 2.5 L Tunair shake flasks or 4 L in 5 L reagent bottles were diluted to a cell density of 4×10^6 /mL. These cells were infected directly with 10-12 mL/L of suspension culture of baculovirus-infected insect cells and incubated at a lowered temperature of 25 °C, at 145 rpm. Infected cells' density and viability along with the cell sizes monitored after 72 hours post-infection time to be able to collect cells for purification at the optimal conditions when Sf9 cells are well infected, usually in 5-6 days after the post-infection time.
Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. Wash Buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 5 mM imidazole 3. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 250 mM imidazole 4. SEC buffer: 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.4), 300 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 5. IEC buffer: 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.4), 260 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 6. TALON beads, equilibrated in Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: IMAC	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spin down cells @6500RPM for 15min 2. Transfer each 1.5L supernatant to a 2.8L flask with 150ml 10X PBS. 3. Add (2ml/L) Ni-sepharose beads to the supernatant and shake at 100RPM at 18 °C for 60 min. 4. Transfer the supernatant + beads to an open column to collect the beads and keep the flowthrough. 5. Wash beads with 50CV of lysis buffer. 6. Wash column with 1CV of wash buffer. 7. Elute protein with 5CV elution buffer. Analyse the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. 8. Add beads (2ml /L) to the collected flowthrough for second binding same condition and repeat the same wash and elution after 1hour shaking.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 26/60 column in SEC buffer at 3 ml/min. 2. Analyze fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity for next step.
Purification step 3: Ion exchange chromatography (IEX)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purify the protein further by Source S, cation exchange chromatography. 2. Elute with concentration gradient of 20 mM HEPES (pH 7.4), 500 mM NaCl, 2 mM TCEP (buffer B). 3. Analyze fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 3 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy.

	4. Snap-freeze aliquots in PCR tubes in liquid N ₂ , and store at -80°C.
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